

Pyrolytic Derangement of S-ethyl N-Disubstituted Dithiocarbamates

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Manuscript received 15 September 1978, accepted 11 January 1979

Pyrolytic decomposition of S-ethyl N-disubstituted dithiocarbamates has been investigated in detail. The main feature of the pyrolytic derangement is the elimination of ethylene and formation of carbon disulphide, N-disubstituted amine and/or trisubstituted thiocarbamide and ethyl mercaptan. Ethyl group on Nitrogen and Sulphur, both are eliminated depending on conditions and nature of substituents. The mechanism has been discussed.

PYROLYSIS of tetraethyl thiuram disulphide, tetraethylthiuram monosulphide and N,N'-diethyl-N,N'-diphenyl thiuram disulphide has been recently reinvestigated by Chande and Tanksale¹. In addition to the products described by earlier workers^{2,3,4} ethylene was found to be eliminated in considerable quantities. A cyclic mechanism has been proposed for this elimination. Since, besides this elimination, decomposition of these compounds along quite a few routes occurred simultaneously, to gain further insight into the process of elimination, pyrolysis of a few simple compounds like ethyl esters of N-disubstituted dithiocarbamates(I) was investigated.

where (i) Ia, R₁=R₂=methyl, (ii) Ib, R₁=Phenyl, R₂=methyl
(iii) Ic, R₁=R₂=phenyl, (iv) Id, R₁=Phenyl, R₂=ethyl
and (v) Ie, R₁=R₂=Ethyl.

On carrying out the pyrolysis of S-ethyl N-dimethyl-dithiocarbamate(Ia) at 265° for 1 hr, dimethylammonium dimethyl dithiocarbamate(II) was obtained as the main product. TLC of the residual reaction mixture showed the presence of II as well as the undecomposed starting material. In the gaseous products, ethylene(III) and traces of hydrogen sulphide were detected. Pyrolysis of S-ethyl N-methyl phenyl dithiocarbamate(Ib) at 315° afforded methylaniline(IVb), carbon disulphide, ethylene and trace amounts of hydrogen sulphide. Pyrolysis of S-ethyl N-diphenyl dithiocarbamate(Ic) at 230-40° gave diphenylamine(IVc), carbon disulphide and ethylene.

Formation of ethylene, in the pyrolysis of the above compounds, is possible by a cyclic elimination reaction involving the β-hydrogen of the ethyl

group and the thion sulphur. Thus

The other products can be formed by further decomposition of the related free dithiocarbamic acid also formed simultaneously :

where IVa, R₁=R₂=Methyl,
IVb, R₁=Phenyl, R₂=Methyl,
IVc, R₁=R₂=Phenyl.

Dimethylammonium dimethyl dithiocarbamate(II), obtained by the pyrolysis of Ia, can arise by the interaction of dimethylamine(IVa) and carbon disulphide.

where Me=Methyl.

Pyrolysis of S-ethyl N-disubstituted dithiocarbamates where at least one of the substituents was an ethyl group appeared to be more complex. For example, on pyrolysis of S-ethyl N-ethyl phenyl dithiocarbamate(Id) at 285°, ethylaniline(V), 1,3-diphenyl-1-ethyl thiocarbamide(VI) and carbon disulphide were isolated along with unreacted starting material. The gaseous products were mainly ethylene and smaller quantities of ethylmercaptan. Formation of V and VI are suggestive of the occurrence of two independent elimination processes operating simultaneously involving in one case the ethyl group on

sulphur and in other part that on the nitrogen. Thus

S-Alkyl N-monosubstituted dithiocarbamates (change : 2 Bii) are known to decompose into the corresponding isothiocyanates and alkyl mercaptans^{5a}.

S-Ethyl N-diethyldithiocarbamate(Ie), on pyrolysis at 250°, gave S-ethyl N-ethyldithiocarbamate(VIII), carbon disulphide, triethylthiocarbamide(IX), ethylene, diethylamine(X) and ethyl mercaptan. The formation of these products can be explained only by mechanisms involving ethyl group(s) substituted on nitrogen as well as sulphur.

3B.

From these results it is evident that the ethyl groups substituted on nitrogen as well as sulphur, both are capable of being eliminated as ethylene. The former is akin to what obtains in the case of tetrasubstituted thiuram disulphides referred to above. The latter, i.e., elimination of S-ethyl group is perhaps akin to what obtains in Chugaev reaction^{5b}.

Experimental

S-Ethyl N-disubstituted dithiocarbamates(I) were prepared by the interaction of the corresponding N-disubstituted dithiocarbamate salt and ethyl bromide^{5c}.

1. *Pyrolysis of S-ethyl N-dimethyl dithiocarbamate (Ia)*: Ia (6 g) was taken in a R. B. flask of 25 ml capacity fitted with a reflux condenser. The gaseous mixture coming out of the assembly was first led through a trap cooled in ice and then through mercuric acetate solution (0.5 g in 25 ml 70% acetic acid). On heating the flask at 265° for 1 hr, a colourless crystalline product was formed in the outer bent tube and in the cold trap which was collected (100 mg). The reaction appeared to be very slow. The compound, m. p. 125°, was highly soluble in water but insoluble in ether. On warming with alkali, smell of dimethylamine was perceptible. It was identified as dimethyl ammonium dimethyldithiocarbamate(II) by its undepressed m.m.p. with an authentic sample of II prepared by the interaction of dimethylamine and carbon disulphide⁵. Its identity was further confirmed by its co-chromatography (TLC) with an authentic sample in ethyl alcohol when a single spot, R_f=0.23, was obtained on development with iodine vapours.

The residual reaction mixture was extracted in acetone. TLC of the acetonetic solution in benzene gave three spots on developing the plate with iodine vapours. The spot, with R_f 0.91, was identified as due to Ia when compared with an authentic sample. The other spot, with R_f 0.52, could not be identified. The spot which did not run was probably due to II. Ia and II were separated by column chromatography using silica (BDH grade) column. On eluting the column with benzene : hexane

(70 : 30), a fraction was collected (60 ml). The solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure when an oil was obtained, b.p. 252°. It was identified as Ia by its co-chromatography with an authentic sample in benzene : hexane (70 : 30) when a single spot was obtained, $R_f=0.76$. On further elution of the column with benzene, a fraction (35 ml) was collected. TLC of the benzene fraction in benzene showed the presence of a faint spot, $R_f=0.52$. It could not be identified. The column was finally eluted with acetone when II was obtained which was identified as described earlier.

TLC of the mercuric acetate solution in *n*-propanol : triethylamine : water (50 : 25 : 25) gave two spots on developing the plate with diphenyl carbazide. The bluish white spot, $R_f=0.713$, was identified as due to ethylene by comparison and co-chromatography with an authentic sample of ethylene prepared by the action of zinc on ethylene dibromide¹. The spot which did not run was probably due to mercuric acetate.

2. Pyrolysis of *S*-ethyl *N*-methyl phenyl dithiocarbamate (Ib) :

The assembly used for the pyrolysis of Ib was the same as described in expt. 1. The gaseous mixture coming out of the assembly was first passed through cold ethereal solution of benzylamine and then through mercuric acetate solution. Ib (3 g) was heated at 310° for 1 hr when a colourless crystalline compound was formed in the trap containing benzylamine which was filtered and washed with ether (450 mg), m.p. 123°. It was identified as benzylammonium benzyl dithiocarbamate through its undepressed m.m.p., with an authentic sample prepared by the interaction of benzylamine with carbon disulphide⁶.

The residual reaction mixture in the flask was extracted with acetone and the solvent distilled off when a syrupy liquid was obtained. TLC of the liquid in benzene : hexane (60 : 40) gave only two spots. The spot with $R_f=0.98$ was identified as due to Ib. The spot with $R_f=0.69$ which was greenish black was identified as due to methylaniline when compared with an authentic sample. The syrupy liquid was triturated with dil. hydrochloric acid and filtered. The filtrate was basified with dil aq. sodium hydroxide (20%) when an oil was obtained which was extracted in petroleum ether (40-60°). On distilling out the solvent, an oil was obtained (0.5 ml), b.p. 192°. It was identified as methylaniline by its co-chromatography with an authentic sample in benzene : hexane (60 : 40) when a single spot was obtained. Its identity was further established by its reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate when 1,3-diphenyl-1-methyl thiocarbamide was obtained, m.p. and m.m.p. 86° with an authentic sample⁷.

TLC of the mercuric acetate soln in propanol : triethylamine : water (50 : 25 : 25) showed the

presence of ethylene which was confirmed by the procedure described in expt. 1.

3. Pyrolysis of *S*-ethyl *N*-diphenyl dithiocarbamate (Ic) :

The assembly used for the pyrolysis of Ic was the same as described in expt. 2. Ic (3 g) was heated at 230°-40° for 1 hr when carbon disulphide and ethylene were formed which were identified as described earlier. The residue was triturated with dil. hydrochloric acid and filtered. The filtrate on treatment with alkali gave diphenylamine (0.51 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 54° with an authentic sample.

4. Pyrolysis of *S*-ethyl *N*-ethyl phenyl dithiocarbamate (Id) :

The assembly used for the pyrolysis of Id is described in expt 2. Id (1.5 g) was heated at 285° for 1 hr when colourless crystalline needles separated out in the trap containing benzylamine. These were identified as benzylammonium benzyl-dithiocarbamate by its m.m.p. (123°) with an authentic sample. TLC of the mercuric acetate solution showed the presence of ethylene. Ethyl mercaptan was identified amongst the gaseous products when these were passed through aq. alkali (20%). On acidification of the alkaline solution with dil. HCl, smell of ethyl mercaptan was perceptible.

The contents in the flask were taken up in acetone. TLC of the acetonic solution in benzene : hexane (60 : 40) gave two spots on development of the plate with iodine vapours. The spot with $R_f=0.813$ was deep yellow in colour and was identified as due to unreacted ester Id by carrying out the co-chromatography with an authentic sample. The other spot which was greenish black in colour ($R_f=0.328$) was due to ethylaniline(V). TLC of the acetonic solution in benzene also showed the presence of Id ($R_f=0.86$) and ethylaniline ($R_f=0.61$) and in addition 1,3-diphenyl-1-ethyl thiocarbamide (VI, $R_f=0.37$), the spot of which was faint yellow and quite small in size.

S-Ethyl *N*-phenyl dithiocarbamate(VII) was not present in the residue as it gave a separate spot ($R_f=0.79$) when co-chromatographed in benzene.

Solvent was removed from the acetonic extract when a syrupy liquid was obtained. This was triturated with dil. HCl and filtered. The filtrate was basified with aq. NaOH (20%) when an oil was obtained which was extracted with *n*-hexane. On distilling out *n*-hexane, ethylaniline (0.5 ml) was obtained, b.p. 205° ($R_f=0.61$ in benzene with authentic sample). Its identity was further established by its reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate, when 1,3-diphenyl-1-ethyl thiocarbamide(VI) was obtained, m.p. and m.m.p. 89°, with authentic sample⁷.

1,3-Diphenyl-1-ethyl thiocarbamide(VI) was present in trace amounts in the residue. It was isolated in detectable amounts by column chromatography using benzene : hexane (60 : 40) and benzene as eluents.

5. *Pyrolysis of S-ethyl N-diethyl dithiocarbamate (Ie)* :

Ie (3 g) was taken in a R. B. flask attached with reflux condenser. The gaseous mixture coming out of the assembly was passed through a trap containing dry ether and through mercuric acetate solution. On heating at 250° for 1 hr, a colourless crystalline compound precipitated out in the first trap. It was filtered and washed with ether, m.p. 81°. It was identified as diethylammonium diethyl dithiocarbamate(XI) by its undepressed m.m.p. (81°) with an authentic sample prepared by the interaction of diethylamine with carbon disulphide^a.

TLC of the mercuric acetate solution in propanol : triethylamine : water (50 : 25 : 25) showed the presence of ethylene.

The reaction residue was taken up in acetone and then chromatographed on a TLC plate using benzene : hexane (70 : 30) when five spots were obtained on development with iodine vapours. The spot, with Rf=0.59, was identified as due to triethyl thiocarbamide(IX) when compared with an authentic sample of IX prepared by the condensation of diethylamine with ethyl isothiocyanate^a. The spots with Rf=0.26 and 0.35 could not be identified. The spot which travelled with solvent front was probably due to Ie. The spot which did not travel was probably due to XI. TLC of the residue in benzene : hexane (40 : 60) gave three spots. The spot with Rf=0.59 was identified as due to S-ethyl N-ethyl dithiocarbamate(VIII) when

compared with an authentic sample prepared by the interaction of ethyl bromide with ethylammonium ethyl dithiocarbamate^a. The spot with Rf=0.81 was identified as due to Ie by comparison with authentic sample. The spot which did not travel was probably due to XI.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks of the author are due to Prof. R. H. Sahasrabudhey for his interest, to Dr. V. V. Deshpande, Head of the Department of Chemistry and Dr. A. Gopalkrishna, Director, Institute of Science, Nagpur for providing necessary facilities.

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